

Panel ARDL Modeling of Tax Revenue

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Abstract

Consistent long-run feedback with inclusive intercepts, country-specific speed of adjustments, short-run returns, and error variances within the descriptive variables by absorption and averaging separate capacities passing thru forceful divergent estimate was utilized to supervise the percentage share of a country's output collected by the government through taxes on income, profit and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes for periods 1970 to 2018 in Denmark, Finland, France, and United Kingdom. The series steadily embraces unit root protocols by gliding about their variances and time-centered dependent are requisite. ARDL (3,2,2,2,2) for three lags and no trend specification depiction was farsightedly selected out of the nine models that were apparent. The deviation from the long-run equilibrium rate in the tax revenue is corrected separately for Denmark, Finland, France and UK, by 35.09%, 18.57%, 8.03% and 2.24% the following year; besides, Denmark is more speedily to the adjustment followed by Finland. All the countries mutually take a speed of -0.159809 to return back to equilibrium; consequently, the deviation from the long-run equilibrium rate in the tax revenue is determined by 15.98% the successive year. Additionally, 1% adjustment in the taxes on income, profit and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes churn out positive weights, 50.46%, 39.37%, 3.88%, and 8.41% discretely on tax revenue. Convincingly, taxes on income, profit and capital gains have a more significant effect on tax revenue's fluctuation for the sub-region followed by taxes on goods and services.

Keywords: ARDL (3,2,2,2,2), Long-run reliability, Speed of adjustment, Tax revenue, Unit root

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Introduction

A key development priority is the collection of taxes and fees as a primary source of income for the government to generate public revenues that make it possible to finance investments in human capital, infrastructure, and the provision of services for citizens and businesses as well as to set the right price incentives for viable private-sector investment (Korkmaz, *et al.* 2019; Bofar, 2003; OECD, 2023).

Taxes are tools of control and regulation for inducing the model of consumption, production and distribution (Hakim and Bujang, 2012). Conferring to World Bank definition, tax revenue (TR) refers to compulsory transfers to the central government for public purposes; certain compulsory transfers such as fines, penalties, and most social security contributions are excluded, refunds and corrections of erroneously collected tax revenue are treated as negative revenue; taxes on income, profits, and capital gains (TIPCG) are levied on the actual or presumptive net income of individuals, on the profits of corporations and enterprises, and on capital gains, whether realized or not, on land, securities, and other assets. Intragovernmental payments are eliminated in consolidation; taxes on goods and services (TGS) include general sales and turnover or value-added taxes, selective excises on goods, selective taxes on services, taxes on the use of goods or property, taxes on extraction and production of minerals, and profits of fiscal monopolies; taxes on social contributions (TSC) include social security contributions by employees, employers, and self-employed individuals, and other contributions whose source cannot be determined, they also include actual or imputed contributions to social insurance schemes operated by governments; and other taxes (OT) include employer payroll or labor taxes, taxes on property, and taxes

not allocable to other categories, such as penalties for late payment or nonpayment of taxes (Bretschger, 2010).

This article examines the effects of Mean Group and the Pooled Mean Group estimator on the percentage share of a country’s output collected by the government through taxes on income, profit and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes for periods 1970 to 2018 in Denmark, Finland, France and United Kingdom.

Materials and Methods

The characteristic effects that are not certain in cross-section or time-series information can be predictable by means of panel data and more composite cooperative models can be substantiated while maintaining smaller amount of constraints (Pesaran, *et al.* 1995; Baltagi, *et al.* 2000; Hsiao, 2003; Martinez-Zarzoso and Bengochea-Morancho, 2004; Baltagi, 2014, 2015). In panel frameworks by means of discrete effects, the link between the mean differenced regressors and the error duration is exciting due to inequity stimulated in the review of autoregressive distributed lag, ARDL models. This inequity only dies away for huge sizes of observations which cannot be adjusted by cumulating the number of cross-sections (Arellano, 2004). Pesaran, *et al.* 1999 projected the pooled mean group estimator that takes the cointegration system of the simple ARDL model and adjusts it for panel scenery by letting the intercepts, short-run quantities and cointegrating relations of the cross-sections to fluctuate transversely (Baltagi and Griffin, 1984, 1997; Pesaran, *et al.* 1997, 1999; Baltagi, *et al.* 2008; Pesaran, 2015).

If V_{it} is representative for all countries $i=1, \dots, N$ (individual-level observations) across all time periods $t=1, \dots, T$ (time series observations) with cross-section dimension subscript i and time as subscript t . The reparametrized error correction equation is prearranged as (Anderson and Hsiao, 1981, 1982; Leuthold, 1991; Baltagi, *et al.* 2003; Gujarati, 2003; Pedroni, 1999, 2004; Hakim and Bujang, 2012):

$$\Delta V_{i,t} = \delta_i D_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \lambda_{i,j} \Delta V_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \Delta S_{i,t-j} \beta'_{i,j} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{1}$$

The adjustment coefficients $\delta_i = -\left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_{ij}\right)$ are expected to be negative annually to reach the steady-state.

$D_{i,t} = V_{i,t-1} - \mu'_i S_{it}$ is the error-correcting speed of adjustment term and $\mu_i = \frac{\sum_{j=0}^q \beta_{ij}}{\left(1 - \sum_k \lambda_{ik}\right)}$ are the long-run

coefficients; If S_{it} has finite autoregressive representations; then, the dependence of instructive variables on the disturbances is allowed when estimating $D_{i,t}$;

$\lambda_{ij} = -\sum_{m=j+1}^p \lambda_{im}$ for $j = 1, 2, K, p-1$ are $(k \times 1)$ vector of parameters constant across groups to be estimated on the dependent variable;

$\beta_{ij} = -\sum_{m=j+1}^q \beta_{im}$ for $j = 1, 2, K, q-1$ are $(k \times 1)$ vector of parameters constant across groups to be estimated on the explanatory variable;

$S_{it} = (s_{i1}, K, s_{iT})'$ are $(T \times k)$ possibly time-varying vector of covariate on k instructive variables that can vary across groups and time periods; while, $\Delta S_i = S_i - S_{i-1} = (\Delta s_{i,1}, \Delta s_{i,2}, K, \Delta s_{i,T})'$ are j lagged values of ΔS_i ;

$V_{it} = (v_{it}, K, v_{iT})'$ are $(T \times 1)$ vectors of observation on the control variable of the i^{th} group; while, $\Delta V_i = V_i - V_{i-1} = (\Delta v_{i,1}, \Delta v_{i,2}, K, \Delta v_{i,T})'$ are j lagged values of ΔV_i ; and

$\varepsilon_{it} = (\varepsilon_{it}, K, \varepsilon_{iT})'$ are time-invariant and accounts for any unobservable individual-specific error term. In order to estimate consistence short-run measurements, it is obligatory that the disturbances are not interrelated with the regressors.

The same number of lags is expected in each cross-section for the dependent variable and the regressors; hereafter, the concentrated log-likelihood function is a product of each cross-section's likelihood given as (Pesaran, 2015; Hakim and Bujang, 2012; Wooldridge, 2010; Gujarati, 2003):

$$L_t(\varphi) = -\frac{T_i}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \log(2\pi\sigma_i^2) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} (\Delta V_i - \delta_i D_i)' M_i (\Delta V_i - \delta_i D_i) \quad (2)$$

where $D_i = (D_{i,1}, D_{i,2}, K, D_{i,T})'$, $M_i = (I_{T_i} - R_i (R_i' R_i)^{-1} R_i')$ and $R_i = (\Delta V_{i,-1}, K, \Delta V_{i,-p+1}, \Delta S_i, \Delta S_{i,-1}, K, \Delta S_{i,-q+1})$.

Pesaran, Shin and Smith (1995) showed that, the mean group (MG) intermediate estimator accepts that the intercept, short-run coefficients, and error variances can swerve across the clusters; while, unweighted averages of different coefficients are calculated for the whole panel. The fixed effect (FE) transitional estimator constrains long-run coefficients to be equal across groups; that is, homogeneity over a single subset of regressors or else countries (Mundlak, 1978; Pesaran, et al. 1995, 1997, 1999; Baitagi, et al. 2000; Hsiao, 2003).

Results and Discussion

The sets of 196 panel data points from World Development Indicator (WDI) of the World Bank for Denmark, Finland, France and United Kingdom (UK) that replicates the percentage share of a country's output collected by the government through taxes levied on income, profits, and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes for periods 1970 to 2018. The choice of these countries was based on the accessibility of data. The graphics, probabilities and consistent measures of the regression were acquired by fitting the imprinting of Eviews10.

The time series plots for log of variables tax revenue (LTR), income, profits, and capital gains (LTIPCG), goods and services (LTGS), social security contributions (LSC) and other taxes (LOT) in figure 1 showed some volatile oscillations in the mean and variances of the series. It would be representative to say that the panel time series data are not covariance stationary by theory; since, they are kaleidoscopic over time and non-uniform spontaneity in the time series continues. Thus, it is essential to validate the unit root structure of the series.

Figure 1: Time series plot of LTR, LTIPCG, LTGS, LSC and LOT

The mean and median of the series are within the maximum and minimum boundaries in table 1. Negative skewness of -0.570824, -0.233336, -0.657727 and -0.406218 for LTIPCG, LTGS, LSC and LOT separately ; and thus, the government may expect frequent small gains and few large losses; but, positive skewness for LTR implies that, the government may expect frequent small losses and a few large gains from tax revenue. Again, their kurtosis levels of 2.418157, 1.943362, 2.306230, 2.108300 and 1.751621 discretely are less than 3.0 normal distribution point of alignment; and so, their curves are platykurtic having fewer values in the tails and fewer values close to the mean. In addition, the Jarque-Bera test probability values of 0.011238, 0.000051, 0.000033 and 0.000116 for LTR, LTIPCG, LSC and LOT were less than 0.05 point of reference and this suggests that the series are non-normal in distribution; but, probability value of 0.057576 for LTGS was greater than benchmark of 0.05 and this suggests that the series is normal in distribution.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	LTR	LTIPCG	LTGS	LSC	LOT
Mean	1.384536	1.460893	1.536414	1.153286	0.387799
Median	1.374860	1.520674	1.543510	1.260167	0.459926
Maximum	1.562296	1.681690	1.706381	1.666136	0.949993
Minimum	1.248508	1.161135	1.339898	0.213985	-0.270849
Std. Dev.	0.074504	0.149291	0.094754	0.444454	0.316142
Skewness	0.436085	-0.570824	-0.233336	-0.657727	-0.406218
Kurtosis	2.418157	1.943362	2.306230	2.108300	1.751621
Jarque-Bera	8.976981	19.76207	5.709313	20.62529	18.11778
Probability	0.011238	0.000051	0.057576	0.000033	0.000116
Sum	271.3691	286.3349	301.1372	226.0441	76.00853
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.082429	4.346112	1.750766	38.52011	19.48937
Observations	196	196	196	196	196

The kernel density plot of figure 2 displays the conception of the series' distribution. The p-values in table 2 are less than 0.05 targets; hence, the series failed to account for the normally distributed null hypothesis assumption; as such, the series are confirmed to be non-normal in distribution.

Figure 2: Kernel density plot of LTR, LTIPCG, LTGS, LSC and LOT

Table 2: Experimental Distribution Tests

Variables	Statistics	Methods		
		Cramer-von Mises (W2)	Watson (U2)	Anderson-Darling (A2)
LTR	Value	0.421985	0.373248	2.670632
	Adj. Value	0.423061	0.374200	2.681008
	p-value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
LTIPCG	Value	1.291488	1.191491	7.709541
	Adj. Value	1.294782	1.194530	7.739494
	p-value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
LTGS	Value	0.129445	0.116965	0.984867
	Adj. Value	0.129775	0.117264	0.988693
	p-value	0.0443	0.0492	0.0131
LSC	Value	1.309861	1.187594	8.139119
	Adj. Value	1.313202	1.190624	8.170740
	p-value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
LOT	Value	1.122236	1.069332	6.852487
	Adj. Value	1.125098	1.072059	6.879109
	p-value	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Unit root tests of LTR, LTIPCG, LTGS, LSC and LOT in table 3, indicated strong evidence in favour of unit root process in the log levels of the series, since their p-values were greater than the 0.05significance level. Hence, the series are non-stationary time series.

Table 3: Unit Root Tests in Levels

Variables	Statistics	Methods			
		Levin,Lin&Chu t*	Im,Pesaran&ShinWstat	ADF-Fisher Chi-Sq.	PP - Fisher Chi-Sq.
LTR	Stat.	-1.12135	-1.05144	15.0974	10.3821
	Prob.	0.1311	0.1465	0.0573	0.2392
LTIPCG	Stat.	0.84547	0.96991	3.24333	4.52173
	Prob.	0.8011	0.8340	0.9182	0.8073
LTGS	Stat.	1.02928	0.05293	5.93868	8.88464
	Prob.	0.8483	0.5211	0.6541	0.3521
LSC	Stat.	1.23760	0.29597	5.13612	9.42085
	Prob.	0.8921	0.6164	0.7429	0.3080
LOT	Stat.	-1.49823	-0.61326	9.84231	8.62333
	Prob.	0.0670	0.2699	0.2763	0.3751

The model selection procedures of table 4, Alkaike information criteria (AIC) make available the minimum value for ARDL(3,2,2,2,2) with the least information criteria values of -6.218913.

Table 4: Model Selection Summary

Model	LogL	AIC*	BIC	HQ	Specification
8	620.139980	-6.218913	-5.380234	-5.878986	ARDL(3, 2, 2, 2, 2)
1	595.441590	-6.211322	-5.791982	-6.041358	ARDL(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)
2	611.155082	-6.208207	-5.509308	-5.924935	ARDL(1, 2, 2, 2, 2)
9	633.170654	-6.186638	-5.068399	-5.733402	ARDL(3, 3, 3, 3, 3)
4	597.143951	-6.186347	-5.697118	-5.988057	ARDL(2, 1, 1, 1, 1)
7	601.102535	-6.185897	-5.626778	-5.959279	ARDL(3, 1, 1, 1, 1)
3	624.655508	-6.181038	-5.202579	-5.784457	ARDL(1, 3, 3, 3, 3)
6	628.542754	-6.179813	-5.131464	-5.754904	ARDL(2, 3, 3, 3, 3)
5	609.829501	-6.150321	-5.381532	-5.838721	ARDL(2, 2, 2, 2, 2)

In table 5, the probable Wald coefficients examination for the designated model ARDL(3,2,2,2,2) are desirably different from zero with statistically importance probability value less than 0.05 point of reference. Thus, the coefficients of the model are dependable.

Table 5: Coefficient Restriction Test

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	49817.66	(4, 148)	0.0000
Chi-square	199270.6	4	0.0000
Null Hypothesis: C(1)=C(2)=C(3)=C(4)=0			
Null Hypothesis Summary:			
Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.	
C(1)	0.504625	0.049245	
C(2)	0.393711	0.046557	
C(3)	0.038843	0.008015	
C(4)	0.084055	0.020822	

Once more, the scaled coefficient diagnostics test of table 6 make available indication and compute boundaries on the estimated quantities. Thus, the estimated coefficients are robust and can be used to make verdicts.

Table 6: Coefficient Constraint Test

Variable	Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	Elasticity at Means
LTIPCG	0.504625	1.011158	0.532454
LTGS	0.393711	0.500716	0.436899
LSC	0.038843	0.231714	0.032355
LOT	0.084055	0.356668	0.023543

In table 7, the coefficient confidence interval tests are within 90, 95, and 99 out of each hundred certitude intervals were obtainable. After that, the coefficients of the model can be said to be reliable and can be used to make pronouncements.

Table 7. Coefficient Confidence Interval Tests

Variable	Coefficient	90% CI		95% CI		99% CI	
		Low	High	Low	High	Low	High
LTIPCG	0.504625	0.423113	0.586136	0.407310	0.601939	0.376121	0.633128
LTGS	0.393711	0.316648	0.470773	0.301708	0.485714	0.272221	0.515200
LSC	0.038843	0.025575	0.052110	0.023003	0.054682	0.017927	0.059758
LOT	0.084055	0.049590	0.118520	0.042908	0.125202	0.029721	0.138389

In table 8, the cross-section renewal coefficient to steadiness of the countries all together is negative as a standard with significance likelihood value; thus, cointegration exists among the variables and the impact of a jolt will be momentary and terminate in the long run as the economy carry on to the steady-state. The coefficients of the independent variables are statistically significance for probability values less than 0.05 conditions. In view of that; at disequilibrium, it takes the nations all in all a speed of -0.159809 to return back to steadiness and the irregularity from long-run improvement percentage is enhanced by 15.98% the consecutive year. Succinctly; in the long-run, 1% change in taxes levied on income, profit and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes will increase the tax revenue by 50.46%, 39.37%, 3.88% and 8.41% individually. All the indicators put into view a positive weight on the long-run elasticity; nevertheless, the positive effect of income, profit and capital gains was more significant on tax revenue.

Table 8: Estimates of Panel ARDL (3,2,2,2,2) Model

Dependent Variable: D(LTR)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Long Run Equation				
LTIPCG	0.504625	0.049245	10.24714	0.0000
LTGS	0.393711	0.046557	8.456468	0.0000
LSC	0.038843	0.008015	4.845973	0.0000
LOT	0.084055	0.020822	4.036846	0.0001
Short Run Equation				
COINTEQ01	-0.159809	0.072108	-2.216259	0.0282
D(LTR(-1))	0.090430	0.065399	1.382755	0.1688
D(LTR(-2))	-0.013581	0.094625	-0.143529	0.8861
D(LTIPCG)	0.250451	0.127610	1.962630	0.0516
D(LTIPCG(-1))	0.053829	0.040084	1.342891	0.1814
D(LTGS)	-0.021375	0.038517	-0.554943	0.5798
D(LTGS(-1))	0.142037	0.104158	1.363672	0.1747
D(LSC)	-0.159902	0.068712	-2.327121	0.0213
D(LSC(-1))	0.045242	0.080697	0.560636	0.5759
D(LOT)	0.027246	0.010061	2.708169	0.0076
D(LOT(-1))	0.029393	0.017154	1.713483	0.0887
Mean dependent var	0.000929	S.D. dependent var	0.016210	
S.E. of regression	0.009756	Akaike info criterion	-5.838163	
Sum squared resid	0.014087	Schwarz criterion	-5.035359	
Log likelihood	620.1400	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-5.513150	

The adjustment coefficient to equilibrium in table 9 was negative as required and statistically significant. At disequilibrium, it takes Denmark a speed of -0.350905 to return back to equilibrium and the deviation from long-run improvement rate is corrected by 35.09% the following year.

Table 9: Cross-Section Short-Run Coefficients for Denmark

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob. *
COINTEQ01	-0.350905	0.006374	-55.05128	0.0000
D(LTR(-1))	0.080869	0.012574	6.431311	0.0076
D(LTR(-2))	0.109680	0.006443	17.02309	0.0004
D(LTIPCG)	0.599026	0.011786	50.82359	0.0000
D(LTIPCG(-1))	0.042342	0.018131	2.335328	0.1017
D(LTGS)	0.009337	0.015132	0.617039	0.5809
D(LTGS(-1))	0.044250	0.012006	3.685595	0.0346
D(LSC)	-0.031202	0.000616	-50.62721	0.0000
D(LSC(-1))	-0.033085	0.000642	-51.55155	0.0000
D(LOT)	0.050988	0.000461	110.6339	0.0000
D(LOT(-1))	0.062747	0.000408	153.6380	0.0000

The adjustment coefficient to equilibrium in table 10 was negative as required and statistically significant. At disequilibrium, it takes France a speed of -0.185658 to return back to equilibrium and the deviation from long-run improvement rate is corrected by 18.57% the following year.

Table 10: Cross-Section Short-Run Coefficients for France

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob. *
COINTEQ01	-0.185658	0.005361	-34.63407	0.0001
D(LTR(-1))	0.271184	0.020290	13.36536	0.0009
D(LTR(-2))	0.177738	0.007897	22.50808	0.0002
D(LTIPCG)	0.124987	0.006685	18.69593	0.0003
D(LTIPCG(-1))	-0.052914	0.007015	-7.542985	0.0048
D(LTGS)	0.061456	0.015236	4.033494	0.0274
D(LTGS(-1))	0.341946	0.014274	23.95644	0.0002
D(LSC)	-0.330396	0.020245	-16.31979	0.0005
D(LSC(-1))	0.181349	0.021322	8.505337	0.0034
D(LOT)	0.014127	0.000668	21.13635	0.0002
D(LOT(-1))	0.025959	0.000657	39.49986	0.0000

The adjustment coefficient to equilibrium in table 11 was negative as required and statistically significant. At disequilibrium, it takes Finland a speed of -0.080289 to return back to equilibrium and the deviation from long-run improvement rate is corrected by 8.03% the following year.

Table 11: Cross-Section Short-Run Coefficients for Finland

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob. *
COINTEQ01	-0.080289	0.000368	-218.0628	0.0000
D(LTR(-1))	-0.039365	0.013855	-2.841180	0.0656
D(LTR(-2))	-0.226414	0.004998	-45.30110	0.0000
D(LTIPCG)	0.267887	0.004955	54.06225	0.0000
D(LTIPCG(-1))	0.132512	0.007238	18.30792	0.0004
D(LTGS)	-0.120293	0.012266	-9.806864	0.0023
D(LTGS(-1))	0.285199	0.012605	22.62508	0.0002
D(LSC)	-0.067762	0.006066	-11.17078	0.0015
D(LSC(-1))	0.177310	0.005876	30.17334	0.0001
D(LOT)	0.036468	0.000147	247.8853	0.0000
D(LOT(-1))	0.045732	0.000153	297.9430	0.0000

The adjustment coefficient to equilibrium in table 12 was negative as required and statistically significant. At disequilibrium, it takes United Kingdom a speed of -0.022386 to return back to equilibrium and the deviation from long-run improvement rate is corrected by 2.24% the following year.

Table 12: Cross-Section Short-Run Coefficients for United Kingdom

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob. *
COINTEQ01	-0.022386	0.000357	-62.74776	0.0000
D(LTR(-1))	0.049033	0.021188	2.314207	0.1036
D(LTR(-2))	-0.115329	0.017243	-6.688275	0.0068
D(LTIPCG)	0.009905	0.023854	0.415247	0.7059
D(LTIPCG(-1))	0.093376	0.023213	4.022570	0.0276
D(LTGS)	-0.036000	0.012656	-2.844383	0.0654
D(LTGS(-1))	-0.103247	0.009492	-10.87682	0.0017
D(LSC)	-0.210249	0.007440	-28.26098	0.0001
D(LSC(-1))	-0.144607	0.007703	-18.77288	0.0003
D(LOT)	0.007402	0.000149	49.52463	0.0000
D(LOT(-1))	-0.016866	0.000153	-109.9898	0.0000

Kao residual cointegration test of no cointegration in the null hypothesis was invalidated for probability values less than 0.05 point of reference in table 13. Thus, cointegration relationship exists amongst the series and thus, the impact of a shock will be momentary and ultimately become extinct as the economy returns to steady state; hence, pairwise Dumitrescu Hurlin panel causality test for individual coefficients might be performed.

Table 13: Kao Residual Cointegration Test

	t-Statistic	Prob.
ADF	-4.528582	0.0000
Residual variance	0.000162	
HAC variance	0.000143	

The pairwise Dumitrescu and Hurlin (2012) tests for two lags in table 14 allows all coefficients to be altered across cross-sections. It can be seen that bidirectional, unidirectional and independent interactions exist between some variables in the model. In view of that, taxes on income, profit and capital gains homogeneously cause tax revenue and vice versa. Also, taxes on goods and services homogeneously cause the taxes on income, profit, capital gains and vice versa. Taxes on goods and services and other taxes homogeneously cause the tax revenue; while taxes on good and services homogeneously cause other taxes. Convincingly, taxes on income, profit and capital gains have a more significant effect on tax revenue's fluctuation for the sub-region.

Table 14: Pairwise Dumitrescu-Hurlin Panel Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	W-Stat.	Zbar-Stat.	Prob.	Decision	Causality
LTIPCG does not homogeneously cause LTR	4.52834	2.19982	0.0278	reject	bidirectional
LTR does not homogeneously cause LTIPCG	7.22973	4.64699	3.E-06	reject	
LTGS does not homogeneously cause LTR	5.75705	3.31290	0.0009	reject	unidirectional
LTR does not homogeneously cause LTGS	1.30958	-0.71604	0.4740	accept	independent
LSC does not homogeneously cause LTR	3.86723	1.60092	0.1094	accept	independent
LTR does not homogeneously cause LSC	2.89252	0.71794	0.4728	accept	independent
LOT does not homogeneously cause LTR	5.87259	3.41757	0.0006	reject	unidirectional
LTR does not homogeneously cause LOT	1.29142	-0.73249	0.4639	accept	independent
LTGS does not homogeneously cause LTIPCG	5.46669	3.04986	0.0023	reject	bidirectional
LTIPCG does not homogeneously cause LTGS	8.98259	6.23490	5.E-10	reject	
LSC does not homogeneously cause LTIPCG	2.84314	0.67321	0.5008	accept	independent
LTIPCG does not homogeneously cause LSC	4.05974	1.77532	0.0758	accept	independent
LOT does not homogeneously cause LTIPCG	4.11617	1.82643	0.0678	accept	independent
LTIPCG does not homogeneously cause LOT	1.06274	-0.93965	0.3474	accept	independent
LSC does not homogeneously cause LTGS	3.43159	1.20628	0.2277	accept	independent
LTGS does not homogeneously cause LSC	2.38486	0.25805	0.7964	accept	independent
LOT does not homogeneously cause LTGS	3.97047	1.69445	0.0902	accept	independent
LTGS does not homogeneously cause LOT	4.85231	2.49331	0.0127	reject	unidirectional
LOT does not homogeneously cause LSC	2.07706	-0.02078	0.9834	accept	independent
LSC does not homogeneously cause LOT	3.83296	1.56988	0.1164	accept	independent

Conclusion

The effects of Mean Group and the Pooled Mean Group estimator on the percentage share of a country's output collected by the government through taxes on income, profit, and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes for periods 1970 to 2018 in Denmark, Finland, France and United Kingdom were investigated. The indicators point to strong evidence in favour of unit root process in the log levels of the series. The pairwise Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel causality tests for two lags revealed that bidirectional, unidirectional and independent interactions exist between some variables in the model. Taxes on income, profit, and capital gains homogeneously cause tax revenue and vice versa. Also, taxes on goods and services homogeneously cause taxes on income, profit, capital gains and vice versa. Taxes on goods and services and other taxes homogeneously cause the tax revenue; whereas taxes on good and services homogeneously cause other taxes. Persuasively, taxes on income, profit and capital gains have a more significant effect on tax revenue's fluctuation for the sub-region. At disequilibrium, it takes the countries completely a speed of -0.159809 to return back to steadiness and the irregularity from long-run improvement percentage is enhanced by 15.98% the consecutive year. Succinctly; in the long-run, 1% change in taxes levied on income, profit and capital gains, goods and services, social security contributions and other taxes will increase the tax revenue by 50.46%, 39.37%, 3.88% and 8.41% individually. The deviation from the long-run equilibrium rate in the tax revenue is corrected separately for Denmark, Finland, France and UK, by 35.09%, 18.57%, 8.03% and 2.24% the following year; besides, Denmark is more speedily to the adjustment followed by Finland.

References

- Anderson, T. W. & Hsiao, C. (1981). Estimation of dynamic models with error components. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 76, 598-606.
- Anderson, T.W. & Hsiao, C. (1982). Formulation and estimation of dynamic models using panel data. *Journal of Econometrics*, 18, 47-82.
- Arellano M., (2004), *Panel Data Econometrics*. Advanced Texts in Econometrics, Oxford University Press.
- Baltagi, B.H. & Griffin, J.M. (1984). Short and Long-run Effects in Pooled Models. *International Economic Review*, 25, 631-645.
- Baltagi, B.H. & Griffin, J.M. (1997). Pooled Estimators versus their Heterogeneous Counterparts in the context of dynamic demand for gasoline, *Journal of Econometrics*, 77, 303-327.
- Baltagi, B.H, Griffin, J.M. & Xiong, W. (2000). To pool or not to pool: homogeneous versus heterogeneous estimators applied to cigarette demand, *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 82, 117-126.
- Baltagi, B.H, Bresson, G., Griffin, J.M. & Pirotte, A. (2003). Homogeneous, Heterogeneous or Shrinkage Estimators? Some empirical evidence from French regional gasoline consumption. *Empirical Economics*, 28, 795-811
- Baltagi, B.H, Bresson, G. & Pirotte, A (2008). To pool or not to pool, p517-546 of Matyas & Sevestre eds *The Econometrics of Panel data*, 3rd edition, Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Baltagi B. H., (2014), *Econometric Analysis of Panel Data*, 5th edition, Wiley.
- Baltagi, B. H. (ed.), (2015). *The Oxford Handbook of Panel Data*, Oxford University Press.
- Bofar, K. (2003). The impact of tax on investment and business decisions. http://www.ehow.com/facts_5910416_impact-tax-investment-business-decisions.html
- Bretschger, L. (2010). Taxes, mobile capital, and economic dynamics in a globalizing world. *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 32, Pp. 594-605.
- Dumitrescu, Elena-Ivona and Christophe Hurlin (2012). Testing for Granger Non-causality in Heterogeneous Panels. *Economic Modeling*, 29, 1450-1460.
- Gujarati, D.N. (2003). *Basic Econometrics*. 4th Edition. Mc Graw Hill Higher Education. New York, USA.
- Hakim, T.A. and Bujang, I. (2012). The Impact and Consequences of Tax Revenues' Components on Economic Indicators: Evidence from Panel Group Data. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 63, Pp. 99-116. DOI: 10.5772/48415.
- Hsiao, C. (2003). *Analysis of Panel Data*. 2nd edition. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Korkmaz, S., Yilgor, M. and Aksoy, F. (2019). The Impact of Direct and Indirect Taxes on the Growth of the Turkish Economy. *Public Sector Economics*, Vol. 43, Issue 3, Pp. 311-323.
- Leuthold, J.H. (1991). Tax shares in developing economies: A panel study. *Journal of Development Economics*, 354, Pp. 173-185.
- Martinez-Zarzoso, I., & Bengochea-Morancho A. (2004). Pooled Mean Group Estimation of an Environmental Kuznets Curve for CO2. *Economics Letters* 82, 121-126.
- Mundlak, Y. (1978). On the Pooling of Time Series and Cross section Data. *Econometrica*, 46, 69-85.
- Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development, OECD (2023). "Tax Revenue" (indicator). <https://doi.org/10.1787/d98bcf5-en>
- Pedroni, P. (1999). Critical Values for Cointegration Tests in Heterogeneous Panels with Multiple Regressors. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 61, 653-70.
- Pedroni, P. (2004). Panel Cointegration; Asymptotic and Finite Sample Properties of Pooled Time Series Tests with an Application to the PPP Hypothesis. *Econometric Theory*, 20, 597-625.
- Pesaran, M.H. & Smith, R.P. (1995). Estimating Long-run relationships from Dynamic Heterogeneous Panels, *Journal of Econometrics*, 68, 79-113.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y. & Smith, R.P. (1997). Estimating long-run relationships in Dynamic Heterogeneous Panels. *DAE Working Papers Amalgamated Series 9721*.
- Pesaran, M.H., Shin, Y. & Smith, R.P. (1999). Pooled Mean Group Estimation of Dynamic Heterogeneous Panels, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 94, 621-634.
- Pesaran, M.H. (2007) A simple panel unit root test in the presence of cross-section dependence, *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 22(2).p265-312.
- Pesaran M.H. (ed.), (2015). *Time Series and Panel Data Econometrics*, Oxford University Press.
- Pesaran, M.H. (2015) *Time-series and panel data econometrics for macroeconomics and finance*. Oxford University Press.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2010). *Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data*. 2nd edition. The MIT Press.